

Janneke Adema, Associate Professor in Digital Media at The Centre for Postdigital Cultures, Coventry University

Driving experimentation

– Janneke Adema

Publishing books open access increases the visibility of research and researchers. It also enables academia to be more creative and to experiment with how research outputs are communicated.

Publishing open access is a natural choice for Janneke Adema. Associate Professor in Digital Media at The Centre for Postdigital Cultures, Coventry University, she has always worked openly. And she has been advocating for change in how and where research is published for many years.

Breaking down barriers

Adema says there shouldn't be any barriers to accessing research. Nor does she believe in waiting to put a finished product out there. When it's suitable and appropriate, she believes in open practice throughout the research lifecycle, from the initial conception of a research idea and the planning stages, data collection and sourcing information, through to analysis and publication. An early blogger, she has regularly invited others to collaborate with her and engage with her work as it progresses. She explained:

“ Communicating my research openly is something I've always done, right from the start of my academic career. I've always put as much as possible on my blog and shared it – my work in progress, my research presentations, my conference presentations and my papers.

Benefiting from working openly

This highly visible and transparent approach has worked well for Adema. It enabled her to create a buzz around her work early on in her career, raising her profile and getting her noticed in academic circles.

She said:

“Being an early adopter of publishing openly has been very beneficial to my career - it meant I made connections with more senior colleagues.”

Publishing openly has given Adema a much bigger, broader reach. It has also made it easier for her research to be used and explored in education settings and in reading groups.

Experimental publishing

Adema thinks open access isn't just about access to research - it breaks down other barriers, such as how research is created and presented. Her work is often processual and multi-modal, with her open access book – Living Books: Experiments in the Posthumanities - being available in several forms. Published by the MIT Press, there is a print, a PDF, and an online version, which can be further updated and commented on. The online version is published on the PubPub platform, hosted by Knowledge Futures, an independent nonprofit organisation founded by the MIT Press and the MIT Media Lab.

Adema wants people to interact with her work, encouraging them to add comments and make annotations and reuse her work in different contexts. She explained:

“ Having more multi-modal, experimental connections around the book has been crucial to the work that I'm doing and the kind of scholarship that I'm arguing for. We need to get books out of their containers.

Alternative, more ethical publishing models

Adema would like to see a community-led, not-for-profit publishing ecosystem thrive. She works with several small, not-for-profit publishers, academics and other people working in scholarly communications who have developed models to publish books without paywalls for readers or charges to authors.

She thinks moving to a different publishing system would enable more experimental forms of publishing to flourish. But, she says there are cultural barriers that need to come down, particularly for early career researchers, who can find it hard to challenge established norms.

Adema said:

“As researchers we’re accustomed to this idea that we’re lucky to get published and we can’t make any demands. It’s hard, particularly as an early career researcher, to push back against that. But you can and there are always options.”

She says community-led presses are often more open to new forms of publishing. Some of them specifically want to help early career scholars, so she advises those starting out in academia to seek them out.